

Electrochemical reduction behaviour of *N*-(benzylidene)-2-aminopyrimidine

T. V. D. Prasad Rao, G. Veerabhadram* and K. S. Sastry

Department of Chemistry, Nizam College, Osmania University, Hyderabad-500 001, India

Manuscript received 7 February 2000, accepted 3 March 2000

N-(Benzylidene)-2-aminopyrimidine has been found to be reduced electrochemically in higher alkaline conditions (pH 9.8–13.0) with uptake of two electrons giving *N*-(benzyl)-2-aminopyrimidine. The products from controlled potential electrolysis (CPE) at mercury pool cathode are characterized. The protonation precedes the electronation in reduction process, which is found to be diffusion-controlled and irreversible from voltammetric techniques. The kinetic parameters such as heterogeneous forward rate constant ($k_{f,h}^0$) and activation free energy change (ΔG) are evaluated. A plausible reduction mechanism has been suggested.

Most of the reports deal with electrochemical reduction of carbonyl compounds both in aqueous and non-aqueous media, but only a few with Schiff bases¹. Pyrimidine as a part of the ring systems of nucleic acids, purines and vitamins plays a vital role in life-processes². Pyrimidine derivatives such as barbiturates are well known for their hypnotic and other biochemical effects³, and drug 3'-azido-3'-deoxythymidine has been approved by FDA for the treatment of AIDS⁴. Hence it was thought worthwhile to study electrochemical reduction behaviour of *N*-(benzylidene)-2-aminopyrimidine derived from 2-aminopyrimidine and benzaldehyde in pH 2.0–13.0. Here, results from dc polarography at DME, cyclic voltammetry and differential pulse polarography at GCE, controlled potential electrolysis at mercury pool cathode and reduction mechanism of the title compound are reported.

Results and Discussion

N-(Benzylidene)-2-aminopyrimidine exhibits a single well-defined cathodic wave (Fig. 1) in the pH range of

Fig. 1. dc polarogram of *N*-(benzylidene)-2-aminopyrimidine at pH 10.30.

9.80–13.0, but no reduction wave is observed below the pH 9.80. The basic nature and electron-withdrawing effect of amine moiety of the title compound are expected to increase with increase in the number of heteroatoms in the heterocyclic ring⁵. Hence it is responsible for reduction of *N*-(benzylidene)-2-aminopyrimidine in higher alkaline conditions.

The diffusion-controlled nature of electrode process is evident from linear plots of i_d vs $h^{1/2}$, i_p vs $v^{1/2}$ and i_m vs $t^{2/3}$, passing through the origin. The irreversibility is indicated by the slopes of log plots $-E$ vs $\log i/(i_d - i)$, and it is found to increase with pH. It is further confirmed by the absence of anodic peak during reverse scan in cyclic voltammograms (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammograms of 1 mM *N*-(benzylidene)-2-aminopyrimidine at pH 10.30 and at scan rates (a) 100, (b) 200 mV s⁻¹.

The half-wave potential ($E_{1/2}$) of *N*-(benzylidene)-2-aminopyrimidine depends on pH and shifts to more negative potentials, indicating that protons are consumed in the reduction process. The $-E_{1/2}$ vs pH plot consists of two linear segments intersecting at pH 10.51. A remarkable

change in $E_{1/2}$ values is observed in the second linear portion whereas a remarkable change in $E_{1/2}$ values is observed below pH 10.51 and the slope value is 0.0846. The similar behaviour of $-E_{1/2}$ vs pH plots are reported in the literature⁶. The nearly constant values of $E_{1/2}$ above pH 10.51 may be due to the fact that acidic and basic forms of depolariser are electroactive at electrode surface, but in the pH range where the equilibrium between basic and acidic

Fig. 3. Differential pulse polarogram of 1 mM *N*-(benzylidene)-2-aminopyrimidine at pH 10.30

forms tends towards basic (unprotonated) form, the half-wave potentials are close to each other⁷. It reveals that protonation precedes the electronation in the reduction process,

The $E_{1/2}$, E_p (peak potential in CV) and E_m (potential at maximum current in DPP) values are found to shift to more negative potentials with increase in concentration of depolarizer indicating the increase in irreversibility of reduction process. The shift in peak potential (E_p) with scan rate (v) in the range 20–300 mV s^{-1} studied, rules out the possibility of fast electron transfer, which is a characteristic feature of reversible process.

The differential pulse polarography has been used for the quantitative estimation of *N*-(benzylidene)-2-aminopyrimidine using both calibration and standard addition methods. The electrochemical reduction of Schiff base above pH 10.51 is increasingly difficult due to less availability of protons. The optimum pH range for quantitative estimation of Schiff base is 9.80–10.51. In the calibration method, the peak current (i_m) is found to vary linearly with concentration of the electroactive species in the range 2.0×10^{-5} to 1.0×10^{-3} M.

The number of protons (p) involved in the rate-determining step is one as determined from the slopes of $-E_{1/2}$ vs pH and log plots. The number of electrons (n) involved in overall reduction process, determined by millimicrocoulometry is found to be two in the entire basic media studied. The kinetic parameters, viz. heterogeneous forward rate constant ($k_{f,h}^0$) and activation free energy change (ΔG)⁸ from dc polarography are reported in the Table 1. The value of $k_{f,h}^0$ decreases whereas ΔG increases with pH, indicating the increasing tendency of irreversibility. The results from all voltammetric techniques, in basic media, suggest that electrode process is irreversible and diffusion-controlled.

Table 1. Kinetic parameters of 1 mM *N*-(benzylidene)-2-aminopyrimidine in buffer solutions

pH	i_d μA	$-E_{1/2}$ V	Slope (S_1) (0.06015/ an_a)	an_a	P (S_2/S_1)	$10^{-18}k_{f,h}^0$ cm s^{-1}	ΔG kcal mol^{-1}
9.80	3.97	1.437	0.0881	0.683	0.961	27.73	30.03
10.30	3.30	1.442	0.0886	0.679	0.955	16.41	30.35
10.51	3.06	1.454	0.0889	0.676	0.952	13.32	30.47
11.02	2.18	1.462	0.0892	0.674	0.948	12.01	30.53
11.55	1.75	1.472	0.0895	0.672	0.938	10.35	30.62
12.05	1.37	1.481	0.0898	0.669	0.945	9.13	30.70
12.83	1.19	1.492	0.0902	0.667	0.938	7.94	30.78

$S_2 = 0.0846$

Table 2. Cyclic voltammetry and differential pulse polarographic data of *N*-(benzylidene)-2-aminopyrimidine at different pH values

Scan rate mV s^{-1}	9.80		10.30		11.02		12.05	
	$-E_p$ or E_m V	i_p μA	$-E_p$ or E_m V	i_p μA	$-E_p$ or E_m V	i_p μA	$-E_p$ or E_m V	i_p mA
Cyclic voltammetry								
20	1.387	1.42	1.431	1.19	1.451	1.03	1.486	0.95
50	1.405	2.18	1.439	1.83	1.459	1.60	1.494	1.49
100	1.419	2.97	1.446	2.45	1.467	2.21	1.500	1.98
150	1.428	3.68	1.451	2.96	1.474	2.73	1.506	2.51
200	1.430	3.92	1.458	3.61	1.479	3.02	1.511	2.84
300	1.439	4.66	1.469	4.16	1.487	3.52	1.519	3.23
DPP								
-	1.432	3.26	1.448	2.91	1.467	2.09	1.489	1.32

Controlled potential electrolysis and reduction mechanism: Controlled potential electrolysis of *N*-(benzylidene)-2-aminopyrimidine was carried out in buffer solutions of pH 10.00 at -1.46 V vs SCE in DMSO. The reduction products of CPE gave no absorption band (λ_{\max}) above 300 nm indicating the absence of azomethine group ($>CH=N-$) in Schiff base. It was further confirmed by negative response to dye test and 2,3,5,6-tetrachlorobenzoquinone test for primary aromatic amines. The reaction mixture was evaporated and then extracted with ether. The ether extract gave one spot on TLC with R_f value 0.81. The comparison of TLC of 2-aminopyrimidine with reduction product shows the absence of 2-aminopyrimidine. The reduction product revealed IR (KBr) peaks at 3427 (NH), 3045 (CH arom.), 1568 (C=N arom.) and 1411 cm^{-1} (C-N) and $^1\text{H NMR}$ signals at δ 8.21 (2H, d, ArH), 7.78 (3H, t, ArH), 7.49 (1H, d, pm-H), 7.24 (1H, q, pm-H), 7.16 (1H, d, pm-H), 4.75 (2H, s, CH_2) and 3.48 (N-H hump). It shows that the $>CH=N-$ group (δ 8.07 s) is electrolytically reduced to $-\text{CH}_2-\text{NH}-$ group and gives secondary amine as product. In the reduction mechanism of *N*-(benzyl)-2-aminopyrimidine after protonation of $>CH=N-$ group in Schiff base, then combines with one electron in a slow step giving free radical. In the following fast step one electron and one proton are consumed and finally yielding *N*-(benzyl)-2-aminopyrimidine secondary amine as a final product (Scheme 1). The probability of dimerization of free radical ion is ruled out as only one wave is observed in voltammetric techniques, and also one spot observed in TLC test

and product analysis of controlled potential electrolysis. The hydrolysis problem does not arise as electrochemical reduction was carried out in non-aqueous buffer solutions.

Experimental

N-(Benzylidene)-2-aminopyrimidine was prepared from 2-aminopyrimidine and benzaldehyde (both A.R.,

Sisco) according to reported method⁹. Stock solutions of Schiff base (1.0×10^{-2} M) were prepared in double-distilled DMSO. The voltammetric experiments were carried out at 303 ± 0.5 K, after deaerating the experimental solution with nitrogen gas for about 20 min. The ionic strength was maintained constant at 0.6 M by adding KCl. The polarograms were recorded with a Toshniwal CL02 polarograph in conjunction with polyflex galvanometer (PL50). The dropping mercury electrode having characteristics of $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.39$ mg, was used as a working electrode and SCE as reference electrode. The cyclic voltammetry and differential pulse polarography experiments were carried out with CS-1090/CS-1087 computer controlled electroanalyzed system (Cypress Systems). The system consisted of three microelectrode assembly in which the glassy carbon electrode (0.5 mm dia) acted as working electrode, silver electrode (0.4 mm dia.) as reference electrode and platinum electrode (0.5 mm dia.) as counter electrode. The CPE was carried out with Potentiostan POS73 (Wenking). The reduction products from CPE were characterized with electronic (Shimadzu 1601 PC), IR (Perkin-Elmer 1605) and $^1\text{H NMR}$ (Varian Gemini, 200 MHz, using TMS) spectra.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (T.V.D.P.R.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for providing financial assistance.

References

1. R. Saiganesh, K. K. Balasubramaniam and C. S. Venkatachalam, *Bull. Electrochem.*, 1990, 6, 515; C. J. Patel, A. S. Madhava, G. Ramachandraiah and D. N. Vyas, *Bull. Electrochem.*, 1995, 11, 159.
2. W. de Gruyter, "Concise Encyclopaedia of Biochemistry". New York, 1983.
3. R. G. Naves and B. Strickland, *Chemistry*, 1974, 47, 15
4. M. K. Gurar, A. C. Kunwar, D. V. Reddy, A. Islam, S. V. S. Lalitha, B. Jagannath and A. V. R. Rao, *Tetrahedron*, 1993, 49, 4373; S. Czernechi and A. Ezzitouni, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1992, 57, 7325.
5. A. Award, F. El-Cheikh and R. Mourad, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1981, 20, 176.
6. W. U. Malik, R. N. Goyal and P. N. Dua, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, 21, 114; R. Jain and D. D. Agrawal, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, 21, 796; R. Jain and S. Gupta, *Bull. Electrochem.*, 1995, 11, 537.
7. P. Zuman, "The Elucidation of Organic Electrode Processes", Academic, London, 1969.
8. L. Meites and Y. Israel, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 4903.
9. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", 3rd ed., Longman, London, 1971.